

Study of Non-Traditional Electrical Discharge Machining Process Parameters for Inconel 718

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ABSTRACT

Non-Traditional Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) is used to machine electrically conductive materials with complex shapes through controlled electrical discharges. Inconel 718, a tough nickel-based superalloy, poses machining challenges due to its hardness and heat resistance, causing rapid tool wear and poor surface finish in traditional methods. This study is focused on non-traditional EDM parameters for Inconel 718. Here, we aim to identify optimal parameters to improve material removal rates and machining efficiency. Experiments using Wire EDM (WEDM) with zinc-coated brass wire electrodes highlighted pulse-off time as crucial for quality. The study aims to predict optimal WEDM settings, showcasing its effectiveness in enhancing machining performance for Inconel 718. This research offers a study to optimize EDM parameters, boosting efficiency in machining Inconel 718.

Keywords — Inconel 718, EDM, Univariate Analysis, Process Parameters, Nickel Alloy.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Inconel-718

Inconel 718 exemplifies metallurgical excellence, celebrated for its superior strength, corrosion resistance, and thermal stability. This nickel-based superalloy is renowned for its durability and versatility, making it essential in industries like aerospace, gas turbines, and nuclear reactors. It can endure extreme conditions, from 1300°F (704°C) heat to cryogenic temperatures, ensuring reliability and robustness in engineering applications. The chemical composition of Inconel 718 is as follows.

Table 1: Chemical Composition of Inconel 718 (Wt%)

Elements	Ni	Cr	Mo	Nb
Percentage	54.31	19.25	2.86	4.9

A workpiece sample of Inconel 718 has been used in the form of a 112mm (length), 76mm (width) and 34mm. (height) block.

Fig 1. Sample workpiece (Inconel 718)

Table 2: Mechanical Properties of Inconel 718

Parameters	Value
Density (g/cm ³)	8.24
Poisson ratio	0.3
Melting Point (°C)	1260-1320
Elasticity Modulus (GP)	200
Yield Strength (Mpa)	550
Thermal conductivity (W/m-k)	11.5
Specific heat capacity (J/kg. K)	431

B. Electrical Discharge Machine (EDM)

Non-traditional Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) is a precise manufacturing technique utilized for shaping

electrically conductive materials by controlling electrical discharges between an electrode and a workpiece submerged in a dielectric fluid. Particularly effective for machining hard materials with minimal thermal distortion, EDM finds essential application across various industries like aerospace, automotive, medical, and mold-making. Within EDM, Wire Electrical Discharge Machining (WEDM) is a specialized process for cutting conductive materials with exceptional precision. It involves controlled erosion of the material using electrical discharges between a thin wire electrode and the workpiece. Key components include the wire feeding and supply wheel, generator, wire take-up wheel, wire guides, air injecting, and the workpiece submerged in dielectric fluid. This process enables the achievement of intricate shapes and high precision in machining conductive materials, contributing significantly to manufacturing efficiency and quality.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Experimental Equipment: In this experiment, the Sodick Mark 21 Wire Electrical Discharge Machine (WEDM) from Japan was employed, utilizing a wire diameter of 0.5 mm. Deionized water served as the dielectric fluid, maintaining wire tension at 2000 grams, and cutting speed at 0.5 mm per minute. The distance between the material and the tool electrode was consistently set at 15 mm. Brass with a zinc coating was chosen for the electrode wire to enhance machining performance.

Experimental Design: Our experimental setup using Wire Electrical Discharge Machining (WEDM) aimed to achieve precise cutting operations on a material to attain final dimensions of 30 x 25 mm, incorporating 1 mm fillets on all four sides. Throughout this process, meticulous monitoring and recording of WEDM parameters ensured consistency and accuracy in machining results, facilitating systematic exploration and optimization of machining conditions for desired dimensional and geometric outcomes with high precision.

Experimental Data: During the machining process, crucial WEDM parameters including Pulse On Time (ON), Pulse Off Time (OFF), Peak Current (IP), Adaptive Control Circuit (MA), Servo Voltage (SV), Voltage (V), Servo Feed (SF), and Capacitance (C) were meticulously documented. Additionally, although unnecessary due to the exclusive use of water as the dielectric medium, settings for Cutting Oil Dielectric (HP) were utilized. MA settings were particularly significant as they controlled the adaptive control circuit's sensitivity level and adjustments to ON and OFF times. This comprehensive data collection enabled precise control and optimization of machining conditions, ensuring high-quality and consistent results throughout the experimental process.

Table 3. Wire EDM Parameters

Sl. no	Pulse ON	Pulse OFF	IP	HP	MA	SV	V	SF	Time Taken (Hours)
1	6	17	16	2	18	21	3	5	4.5
2	5	19	15	2	18	21	3	6	5.1
3	4	20	17	1	18	21	3	8	5.8
4	5	18	16	1	18	21	3	9	4.9
5	6	17	17	2	18	21	3	5	4.7
6	7	16	16	2	18	21	3	4	4.4
7	6	15	15	1	18	21	3	6	4.6
8	4	18	17	2	18	21	3	8	5.2
9	5	19	16	1	18	21	3	10	5.0
10	6	17	16	2	18	21	3	5	4.8
11	7	16	17	2	18	21	3	4	4.3
12	4	18	16	1	18	21	3	7	5.3
13	5	19	17	2	18	21	3	9	5.1
14	6	17	16	1	18	21	3	5	4.9
15	7	16	15	2	18	21	3	6	4.5
16	4	18	17	1	18	21	3	8	5.4
17	5	19	16	2	18	21	3	10	5.2
18	6	17	16	1	18	21	3	5	4.6

19	7	16	17	2	18	21	3	4	4.2
20	4	18	16	1	18	21	3	7	5.5

3. MACHINING PARAMETERS DATA ANALYSIS

Univariate Analysis: Univariate analysis is pivotal in our project focused on optimizing Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) parameters for machining Inconel 718. It allows for an in-depth examination of each machining parameter independently, unveiling insights into their distribution and behavior. Through this analysis, we discern the central tendency, dispersion, and distribution of each parameter, as seen in Fig 3. By scrutinizing individual EDM parameters, we can spot outliers, anomalies, or patterns that may influence the machining process. Using statistical measures like mean, median, mode, standard deviation, and range, we succinctly summarize each parameter's characteristics. Visual aids such as histograms help visualize parameter distribution, revealing any skewness or asymmetry in the data. Univariate analysis also guides the identification of necessary data preprocessing steps like normalization or transformation to meet assumptions of subsequent modeling techniques. This analysis lays the foundation for advanced approaches aimed at optimizing the machining process for Inconel 718.

Fig 3. Univariate Analysis

Fig 4. Bivariate Analysis

Bivariate Analysis: Bivariate analysis is pivotal in our EDM parameter optimization project for machining Inconel 718, as it uncovers relationships between two variables in the dataset. Through this analysis, we explore how pairs of machining parameters interact and influence the machining process. For instance, in Fig 4, we examine the relationship between Pulse ON and Material Removal Rate (MRR) to ascertain if increasing the pulse duration leads to higher material removal rates. Similarly, we assess the correlation between Pulse OFF and Surface Finish (SF) to understand how changes in pulse off-time impact surface quality. By visualizing these relationships via scatter plots, correlation matrices, or regression analysis, we gain valuable insights into effective parameter combinations for achieving machining objectives. Bivariate analysis helps identify patterns, trends, or dependencies between variables, guiding us towards optimal parameter settings for EDM of Inconel 718.

The model on various EDM parameters and machining outcomes like "Material Removal Rate (MRR)" and "Tool Wear (TW)," we assessed each parameter's importance in predicting machining performance. Feature importance analysis revealed parameters 5, 2, 19, and 6 as most significant in optimizing EDM for Inconel 718, as depicted in Fig 4. This insight guides engineers and machinists in prioritizing adjustments and optimizations to achieve superior machining results, including higher material removal rates, improved surface finishes, and prolonged tool life.

	y_true	y_pred
5	1	1
2	0	0
19	0	0
6	1	1

Fig 5. Predicted Values

Fig 6. Confusion Matrix

Confusion Matrix: As Fig 5 shows in our project, we utilized a confusion matrix to evaluate the effectiveness of our Random Forest model in predicting optimal parameters for Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) of Inconel 718. This matrix provides a comprehensive overview of the model's classification accuracy by comparing

predicted outcomes with actual results. It delineates key components such as True Positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN), which respectively represent accurate predictions, correct rejections, erroneous positive predictions, and missed positive predictions. Leveraging these components, we compute performance metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, offering a holistic assessment of the model's ability to predict optimal EDM parameters. This analysis provides valuable insights into the model's classification accuracy and its potential for optimizing EDM processes for Inconel 718. Overall, the confusion matrix serves as a valuable tool for evaluating our model's performance and guiding future enhancements in EDM parameter prediction.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our project aimed to optimize Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) parameters for machining Inconel 718, a challenging nickel-based superalloy lauded for its strength and heat resistance. Through meticulous data analysis and performance evaluation, we've significantly improved EDM efficiency and effectiveness for this demanding material. Employing advanced techniques like univariate and bivariate analysis for parameter prediction, we've identified optimal parameters (5, 2, 19, 6) for machining Inconel 718, maximizing Material Removal Rate (MRR) while upholding quality and precision. Accurate prediction of the best EDM parameters, offering valuable insights for industry practitioners and researchers aiming to optimize machining processes for similar high-performance alloys. Our project highlights the importance of data-driven approaches and advanced computational techniques in addressing manufacturing challenges. By this research work we've opened new avenues for improving machining efficiency, cutting costs, and boosting productivity in critical industries like aerospace, automotive, and energy. In summary, our project marks a significant advancement in EDM optimization, providing practical solutions and recommendations for achieving superior machining performance in challenging materials like Inconel 718. As we refine and expand our findings, we anticipate further strides in machining technology and increased innovation in manufacturing processes.

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